

Mesh Tally Adaptive Mesh Refinement Strategies for Spatial Gradients Driven by Material Heterogeneities

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ABSTRACT

Monte Carlo transport methods have gained popularity in recent years for single-physics and multi-physics reactor analysis, due in part to the minimal assumptions inherent to the method and the rise in computing resources available. However, the specification of tallies in Monte Carlo simulations requires a great deal of analyst expertise to balance spatial fidelity, runtime, and statistical error. This work builds off of previous work that added adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) capabilities from MOOSE to OpenMC via Cardinal to reduce the amount of *a priori* knowledge required by analysts. Two new error estimators are presented that are based on prior literature for AMR and mesh refinement in deterministic transport. These estimators are combined with an adaptivity algorithm commonly used in finite element problems based on error fractions, and a modified form of this adaptivity algorithm that is better suited to applications involving stochastic solvers. These techniques are applied to two test problems exhibiting material property driven gradients. It was found that the new estimators perform quite well and converge to the reference solution for problems with strong gradients within single spatial regions. The modified adaptivity algorithm proposed in this work remedies the non-convergence problems previously observed for Monte Carlo tallies. However, these techniques appear to fail in problems with weak intra-region gradients (such as a 1D SFR problem) as the algorithms presented in this work force refinement on every active adaptivity cycle.

Keywords: AMR, Monte Carlo Transport, Unstructured Mesh Tallies, Cardinal, OpenMC

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, analysts have been more readily turning to Monte Carlo transport methods to act as the neutronics solver in single-physics and multi-physics analyses of nuclear reactors. While Monte Carlo methods have many advantages over deterministic approaches for modern reactor analysis, they require substantial expertise from analysts during the specification of tallies. Spatial tallies in a reactor model must balance runtime and statistical error while attempting to maximize spatial accuracy. This is further complicated by the propagation of spatial and statistical error from tallies to other fields in multiphysics simulations, which requires *a priori* knowledge of the interplay between various physics for reactor concepts that are still under active development. Adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) mitigates these challenges by placing additional degrees of freedom (DOFs) in regions of interest automatically (which may change location during transients or multi-physics iterations). AMR can coarsen the mesh tally in low-importance regions, decreasing the number of elements to minimize the runtime penalty of tallying and the statistical penalty inherent to refining tally bins. The use of AMR lowers the barrier to entry for high-fidelity analysis by decreasing the amount of *a priori* knowledge required by an analyst.

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Previous work applying AMR to radiation transport has largely focused on deterministic methods. Examples include refinement based on residual evaluations of the discretized discrete ordinates (S_N) transport equation [1], heuristics such as the jump of the gradient of the scalar flux [2] or angle-integrated jump of the neutron current [3]. The application space to Monte Carlo methods thus far includes refining or coarsening the mesh based on the magnitude of the approximated tally gradient in an element [4] or refining the mesh used for weight windows based on the reaction rate in an element [5]. These previous Monte Carlo AMR approaches are limited to structured meshes in single-physics analysis scenarios. Recently, unstructured mesh tally AMR capabilities have been added to OpenMC [6] via the multi-physics driver application Cardinal [7, 8]. This work extends [8] by proposing an AMR algorithm that mitigates cyclic non-convergence and prevents regional overrefinement, while evaluating the performance of several heuristic-based error estimators for simplified problems where refinement is driven by material discontinuities (as opposed to neutronics boundary conditions as studied in [8]).

The remainder of this work is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the software implementation of AMR within Cardinal. This is followed by a description of the error estimators investigated in this work, the previous refinement algorithm from [8], and the new refinement algorithm that removes cyclic non-convergence of refinement sequences. The techniques are then applied to two simplified test problems in Section 3. Section 4 presents some concluding results and areas for future work.

2. COMPUTATIONAL METHODOLOGY

The strategy used to apply the Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) [9] and libMesh [10] adaptivity systems to unstructured mesh tallies in OpenMC through Cardinal was originally described in [8]. A summary of the scheme can be found in Fig. 1. In order to be effective, this adaptivity framework must be combined with robust algorithms for determining lists of elements that should be isotropically refined (split into self-similar elements) or coarsened, and accurate methods for estimating the spatial discretization error within a given element. The remainder of this section describes the methods used in this work.

Figure 1. AMR scheme as-implemented in Cardinal [8].

2.1. Refinement Algorithms

Initial experiments with mesh tally AMR in Cardinal primarily used Alg. 1, known as the ErrorFractionMarker in MOOSE [8]. The objective of this algorithm is to refine elements that compose the upper fraction of the total spatial error. Elements are sorted into a list such that the error metric for each element, $e_n(elem)$, is monotonically decreasing, while the total error is summed across all elements. The sorted element list is then iterated; elements with a cumulative error sum (computed from largest to smallest error) less than or equal to a fraction c of the total error are then marked for refinement. $c = 1$ marks all elements for refinement while $c = 0$ marks no elements for refinement. The refinement list is then post-processed to ensure the statistical error in the problem remains bounded. Elements are only refined if their statistical relative error (e_s) is below a user specified refinement threshold \tilde{t}_{refine}

and Alg. 1 determines whether the element should be refined. If the statistical relative error in an element $e_s(elem)$ is above a user specified coarsening threshold $\tilde{t}_{coarsen}$, the element is coarsened instead of refined.

This approach has two main disadvantages: the growth of the number of elements is only bounded by the number of adaptivity cycles, and the adaptivity state of the mesh may not converge due to statistical fluctuations in individual mesh tally bins [8]. This work proposes a modified version of Alg. 1 to address these disadvantages by removing high variance elements from the total spatial error calculation while “looking ahead” to estimate the statistical error of child elements post-refinement and only refining elements with child “look-ahead” statistical error below the threshold. The first modification is to compute the cumulative sum of spatial error over the subset of elements that meet \tilde{t}_{refine} (the first loop in Alg. 2). The second modification is to only refine an element if the estimate of the statistical relative error post refinement, $e_{s,lh}$, is less than \tilde{t}_{refine} . $e_{s,lh}$ is derived under the assumption that the distribution of statistical relative error is constant within an element pre-refinement. This leads to the following definition for an estimate of the statistical error in an element after a refinement operation is performed based on the volume prior to a split (V_j) and the volume of a child element after a split (V_{j+1}):

$$e_{s,lh} \propto e_s \sqrt{\frac{V_j}{V_{j+1}}}. \quad (1)$$

The ratio between the volume terms is equal to the number of child elements N_c for isotropic refinement (e.g., $N_c = 8$ for hexahedral elements). A summary of the look-ahead adaptivity algorithm can be found in Alg. 2. In the event the mesh is unchanged after either Alg. 1 or Alg. 2 finishes executing, all remaining adaptivity cycles are skipped.

Algorithm 1 Error fraction refinement scheme.

Require: $elems, c, \tilde{t}_{refine}, \tilde{t}_{coarsen}$
 $sorted \leftarrow sort(elems)$
 $\mathcal{E}_t \leftarrow sum(e_h(elems))$
 $\mathcal{E}_{accum} \leftarrow 0$
for $elem \in sorted$ **do**
 $\mathcal{E}_{accum} \leftarrow \mathcal{E}_{accum} + e_h(elem)$
 if $\mathcal{E}_{accum} \leq c \times \mathcal{E}_t$ & $e_s(elem) < \tilde{t}_{refine}$ **then**
 mark_refine($elem$)
 end if
end for
for $elem \in sorted$ **do**
 if $e_s(elem) > \tilde{t}_{coarsen}$ **then**
 mark_coarsen($elem$)
 end if
end for

Algorithm 2 Look-ahead error fraction refinement scheme.

Require: $elems, c, \tilde{t}_{refine}, \tilde{t}_{coarsen}$
 $sorted \leftarrow sort(elems)$
 $\mathcal{E}_t \leftarrow 0$
for $elem \in sorted$ **do**
 if $e_s(elem) \leq \tilde{t}_{refine}$ **then**
 $\mathcal{E}_r \leftarrow \mathcal{E}_t + e_h(elem)$
 end if
end for
 $\mathcal{E}_{accum} \leftarrow 0$
for $elem \in sorted$ **do**
 $e_{s,lh} \leftarrow e_s(elem) \times \sqrt{N_c(elem)}$
 if $e_{s,lh} \leq \tilde{t}_{refine}$ **then**
 $\mathcal{E}_{accum} \leftarrow \mathcal{E}_{accum} + e_h(elem)$
 if $\mathcal{E}_{accum} \leq c \times \mathcal{E}_r$ **then**
 mark_refine($elem$)
 end if
 end if
end for
for $elem \in sorted$ **do**
 if $e_s(elem) > \tilde{t}_{coarsen}$ **then**
 mark_coarsen($elem$)
 end if
end for

2.2. Error Estimators

Gradients in radiation fields are primarily driven by three phenomena: strong radiation sources, radiation streaming, and attenuation due to the interaction of particles with a bulk media. Motivated by the success of the optical depth as a refinement criteria in previous work and the use of the inverse of the optical depth when generating unstructured mesh Method of Characteristics (MOC) source regions [11], an *inverse optical depth estimator* is proposed in this work:

$$e_{\tau,i,x} = \frac{1}{\tilde{\Sigma}_{i,x} h_{cr}}, \quad (2)$$

where $e_{\tau,i}$ is the inverse optical depth error estimate, $\tilde{\Sigma}_{i,x}$ is an effective single-group macroscopic cross section (cm^{-1}), and h_{cr} is an estimate of the chord length of the element (cm) using the cube-root of the element volume. Subscript i indicates a mesh element and subscript x indicates a specified reaction. $\tilde{\Sigma}_{i,x}$ is computed using reaction rate and flux tallies in OpenMC:

$$\tilde{\Sigma}_{i,x} = \frac{\int_{V_i} \int_{4\pi} \int_0^\infty \Sigma_x \psi \, dE \, d\Omega \, dV}{\int_{V_i} \int_{4\pi} \int_0^\infty \psi \, dE \, d\Omega \, dV}, \quad (3)$$

where Σ_x is the continuous energy macroscopic cross section (cm^{-1}) for reaction x , ψ is the angular neutron flux ($\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{str}^{-1} \text{eV}^{-1}$), and V_i is the volume of an element (cm^3). The use of the inverse optical depth estimator causes refinement in regions of high reaction rate density, capturing gradients caused by particle interactions with the background media, and through an appropriate selection of reaction channel x (such as fission), it can also capture the formation of sources that are a function of the particle flux. In addition to the inverse optical depth estimator, this work also proposes the *current jump estimator* based on previous works using a similar estimator in S_N transport [3]:

$$e_{cur,i} = \sqrt{h_{max,i} \oint_{S_i} [[\hat{n} \cdot \vec{J}_{net}]]_i^2 \, dS}, \quad (4)$$

where $e_{cur,i}$ is the current jump error estimate, $h_{max,i}$ is the maximum vertex separation in an element, S_i is the element surface, \hat{n} is the outwards facing surface normal of the element, \vec{J}_{net} is the net current vector (constructed with a spherical harmonics expansion), and $[[u]]_i$ is the jump operator acting on a scalar field u . The jump operator returns the difference between the values of u on different sides of S_i . The current jump estimator assumes that the spatial error in a problem is proportional to the change in the net current between two elements. Eq. 2 and Eq. 4 are compared with the standard approach for discontinuous field variables in the MOOSE framework, the *value jump estimator*:

$$e_{jmp,i} = \sqrt{h_{max,i} \oint_{S_i} [[u]]_i^2 \, dS}, \quad (5)$$

where $e_{jmp,i}$ is the jump error estimate. h_{cr} is used over h_{max} for $e_{\tau,i,x}$ based on previous experiments using the single-group optical depth as an error estimator as it results in less spurious over-refinement [8].

3. RESULTS

In this section, the AMR methods discussed in this work are applied to a series of simplified one-dimensional (1D) test problems. These problems are designed to introduce material property driven gradients, while testing the behavior of adaptivity across a range of different neutron spectra. The first test problem represents a simplified light water reactor (LWR) lattice cell with alternative UO_2

fuel pins and three empty guide tubes; the guide tubes are placed to introduce strong gradients in pin power densities (Fig. 2a). The second test problem represents a simplified sodium fast reactor (SFR) lattice cell with fuel pins that include different plutonium/uranium enrichments. The addition of “higher enriched” (HE) fuel pins on the periphery of the “lower enriched” (LE) pins serves to introduce gradients across across the test problem that are normally weaker in SFR assemblies (Fig. 2b).

Parameter sweeps across both test problems are run with 10000 particles per batch, 10 inactive batches, 100 active batches, and 10 adaptivity cycles. Additional inactive batches were not found to be necessary to converge the fission sources for these simplified problems. The initial non-uniform tally mesh is the coarsest mesh possible that perfectly captures the OpenMC constructive solid geometry (CSG). Fission heating is chosen as the tally score to refine with AMR as it is highly discontinuous, exhibits strong gradients within fissile regions (in thermal spectrum reactors), and often a quantity of interest in multi-physics analysis. Accordingly, the fission reaction rate is tallied to compute Eq. 2 and an order one spherical harmonics expansion of the angular flux is tallied per-element to reconstruct the net current for Eq. 4. The error fraction c is varied between 0.1 and 0.5, while the refinement relative error threshold \tilde{t}_{refine} was set to 5% and the coarsening error threshold $\tilde{t}_{coarsen}$ was set to 10%. Results are compared to a reference calculation that is performed on the initial mesh after it has been uniformly refined five times. To eliminate statistical error in comparisons, the reference uses 100000 particles per batch, 10 inactive batches, and 1000 active batches. The input files required to recreate the results presented in this section can be found at https://github.com/neams-th-coe/cardinal_amr.

Figure 2. 1D test problems chosen for this work.

The L_2 difference between the adaptive solution and the reference solution for the LWR problem can be found in Fig. 3 alongside the number of elements. Both quantities are plotted as a function of adaptivity cycle and the error fraction c . When an adaptivity sequence terminates early due to an unchanging mesh, the line is plotted to the last executed adaptivity cycle. The use of Alg. 2 is indicated by (LH) in the legend of both plots; other lines use Alg. 1. In general, the number of elements increases quite dramatically for the inverse optical depth estimator, followed by a more modest increase in the value jump and slow increase in the number of elements added by the current jump. The L_2 error follows a similar trend, where the the optical depth estimator results in a large initial decrease in the L_2 difference before the refinement sequence is terminated. The value jump also exhibits the same behavior, albeit at a far slower rate. As opposed to both the inverse optical depth and the value jump estimators, the current jump results in a far slower decrease in the L_2 difference with the reference solution. However, it is capable of reaching a similar endpoint as the more aggressive estimators with fewer elements. The use of the look-ahead scheme with all error estimators results in a substantial decrease in the number of elements added due to early termination of the refinement sequence.

Similar to the LWR case, the L_2 difference and number of elements for the SFR problem can be found in Fig. 4. The results from this parameter sweep stand in stark contrast to the results from the LWR case, where it appears as though AMR results in no improvement to the L_2 difference in the solution. This is primarily due to the fairly weak gradients within pins, resulting in flat power distributions and L_2 differences that are substantially smaller than the statistical relative error in a tally bin. Algorithms such as the ones presented in this work that focus exclusively on refining the tally mesh are not well

suiting to problems with weak spatial gradients. The use of a refinement fraction results in continual refinement on every adaptivity cycle which is only bound by statistical error. Future work should include extending Alg. 2 to perform coarsening in a statistics-informed manner, and the adoption of mesh tally amalgamation to create logical elements to avoid the runtime penalty of overrefinement [12].

Figure 3. Aggregate results for the parameter sweep of different AMR approaches applied to the LWR test problem.

Figure 4. Aggregate results for the parameter sweep of different AMR approaches applied to the SFR test problem.

The spatial distribution of AMR results (compared to the reference) can be found in Fig. 5 and 6 for

$c = 0.3$ and cycle three, where the trends observed in the aggregate data can be confirmed. Cycle three was chosen as it represents the largest difference between the spatial refinement sequences for all three schemes. In both the LWR and SFR problem, the inverse optical depth estimator refines uniformly over the majority of the domain. The current jump and value jump both prioritize refinement near material heterogeneities as opposed to uniformly within fuel pins. The spurious overrefinement can be confirmed in the SFR problem, where the tallied fission heating is quite flat over single pins and statistical error within AMR mesh tally bins dominates. It is important to note that it is difficult to draw conclusions about the usefulness of each adaptivity scheme presented in this work purely based on a difference with a reference solution, the number of elements added per cycle, or the number of Monte Carlo calculations performed. Future works should define a figure of merit (FOM) that incorporates the desire to minimize runtime, statistical error, and spatial discretization error to allow for the formation of quantitative conclusions regarding the efficacy of the presented AMR schemes.

Figure 5. Spatial refinement behavior of different error estimators (using Alg. 2) for the LWR problem. a) inverse optical depth. b) current jump. c) value jump.

Figure 6. Spatial refinement behavior of different error estimators (using Alg. 2) for the SFR problem. a) inverse optical depth. b) current jump. c) value jump.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents two new error estimators for unstructured mesh tally AMR in Monte Carlo transport simulations that are based on heuristics derived from the behavior of radiation fields. These error estimators are combined with error fraction refinement algorithm commonly used with AMR in a finite element context. A modified version of this algorithm (deemed a *look-ahead error fraction*) is then presented that mitigates the cyclic non-convergence previously quantified while terminating the adaptivity sequence early to reduce cost. The inverse optical depth and value jump estimators performed the best in the LWR test problem, while the current jump estimator resulted in a more gradual refinement sequence. The look-ahead algorithm provided the intended benefit, removing cyclic non-convergence and terminating the refinement sequence early to prevent an undue statistical penalty compared to the L_2 difference. Future work for single physics mesh tally AMR should include the application of coarsening and tally element amalgamation to better capture the physics in systems with weak per-pin spatial gradients (such as the SFR problem). A FOM for AMR *must* be specified to enable quantitative comparisons between different adaptivity strategies that consider the desire to minimize spatial discretization

error, statistical error, and runtime. Finally, a non-trivial but necessary extension of these techniques is to multi-physics simulations, where the added DOFs improve the accuracy of predicted safety metrics (such as peak cladding temperature). This will require a completely different set of error estimators that propagate error in temperature fields to the corresponding spatial discretization error in the neutronics mesh tally.

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